

WHAT

OHRAS Activities

The key of OHRAS is collectively working towards a world with less zoonotic disease burden through collaboration between the sectors of veterinary, human and environmental health and food safety, at all levels.

The OHRAS consists of 6 activities, to be performed in a OH fashion:

OH Signalling

Share information on zoonotic events with relevant organisations across sectors.

OH Risk assessment

Scientific analysis of information on zoonotic hazards to provide risk managers with a risk estimate in a structured way.

OH Feasibility assessment

Weigh suggested measures to reduce zoonotic risks by taking into account factors such as practicality, proportionality and acceptability, for/with relevant stakeholders.

OH Risk management

Coordinate decision making on measures to prevent and control the effects of zoonotic diseases.

OH Risk communication

Provide coordinated messages about the outcome of the OHRAS activities to the public at risk as well as other relevant stakeholders.

OH Governance

Give vision and direction to the activities of OHRAS ensuring clear and supported ways of working.

Terms of Reference (ToR)

Guidance to draw ToR per activity is given.

Tools

Tools are available to support each OHRAS activity.

Website

Guidelines for setting up a OHRAS. Development by OHEJP project COHESIVE. Will be announced at: www.onhealthejp.eu/jip-cohesive

